

December 23, 2013

Dear Madam Quinn:

Thank you for your response to our letter. We are pleased to learn that the Cochrane Gynaecological and Orphan Cancer Group took action following our inquiry of December 2012.

However, we would still like some further clarification of a few points in your response that remain vague and hope you can provide some details. Specifically.

- What criteria will be used to select authors of future reviews: or have they already been chosen?
- What conflicts of interest criteria/processes has the Cochrane Gynaecological and Orphan Cancer Group established that would exclude an author?
- Does the Cochrane Gynaecological and Orphan Cancer Group itself verify the accuracy of declarations of conflicts of interest of potential or current authors and, if so, how is this done?

We look forward to your responses to these few questions, and thank you in advance for your help.

Sincerely,

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